

Chemical components of Mandarin species : A review

Lalita Yadav and S. B. Kalidhar*

Department of Chemistry, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004, Haryana, India

E-mail : sbkalidhar@gmail.com

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Abstract : Mandarin species are known to contain flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, limonoids, coumarin and steroids. These plants are associated with several biological activities.

Keywords : Mandarin, *Citrus reshni*, *Citrus pectinifera*, other *Citrus* species, Rutaceae, flavonoids, terpenoids.

Introduction

Mandarin is a group named for loose skinned oranges which have been dubbed "kid glove" oranges. Mandarins are considered to be a native of South-Eastern Asia and Philippines. These are abundantly grown in Japan, Southern China and India. Mandarin is "mikan" of Japan, "suntra"; "sangtra" of India and "Mandarino" of Italy and Spain. Tanaka concludes that mandarin is indigenous to Nepal. Mandarins are cultivated in southern region of Brazil, covering an area of 12000 ha¹.

Citrus pectinifera (Tan.)/*C. depressa* and *C. reshni* (Tan.) belong to the family Rutaceae². These are mandarin oranges. *Citrus* fruits have prominent place among popular and extensively grown tropical and subtropical fruit. Except grapes and olives, these are cultivated on larger area than any other fruit of these zones in world⁴.

C. reshni is "billi kichili" of India and "cleopatra mandarin" of the United States. Trees are round-topped, symmetrical and thornier with small dark green leaves. The fruit is orange-red, small oblate and highly depressed at the apex, with somewhat rough rind. The flesh texture is soft and juicy, seeds are small, polyembryonic and have green cotyledons and are 20 or more³. *C. pectinifera* is, sometimes called as Taiwan tangerine and thin-skinned flat lemon. This species is the "shiikuwasha" of Okinawa and Taiwan and "shekwasha" or "sequasse" in United States. The tree is vigorous, round-topped and finely stemmed. The fruit is very small orange coloured, oblate and highly depressed at both ends with very thin, loose and aromatic rind. The flesh is soft, gelatinous and acidic. Fresh juice is very sour.

C. reshni is increasingly important as rootstocks in United States⁵. Scions budded on cleopatra mandarin are large and moderately vigorous⁶, producing deep, densely branched root system imparting moderate drought tolerance. Cleopatra shows tolerance to major citrus virus diseases⁷. Fruits of the mandarin plant are believed to act as deodorant, aphrodisiac, appetiser, digestive, liver tonic, alexeteric, disinfectant; useful in vomiting, pectoral diseases, anorexia, dyspepsia, cardiac disorder and vitiated conditions. Flowers are stimulant, diuretic, sedative febrifuge tonic against *pitta* and *vatta*. External application of poultice made of heated fresh leaves and decoction of dried leaves taken by mouth are prescribed for the treatment of colic and mastitis⁸. Juice mixed with a glass of tender coconut water is a very valuable natural diuretic in all conditions of scanty gonorrhoeal, painful micturation and non-specific urethrities⁹. Volatile oil from leaves shows antibacterial activity¹⁰.

A number of flavonoids are reported from different parts of mandarin species and details of the same are given in Table 1. Of these natsudaids (43), nobiletin (48), tangertin (56), and 3,5,6,7,8,3',4'-heptamethoxyflavone (1) have been isolated from juice of *C. nobilis*¹¹.

A recent study indicates that nobiletin (48), a polymethoxylated flavone, which accumulates in shikuwasha fruits (*C. depressa* Hayata), exhibits anticarcinogenic activity¹². Tangertin (56) is reported to have suppressive effects on malignant tumor invasion and metasis¹³. Ponkan (*C. reticulata*) contains a wide variety of bioactive compounds such as polymethoxylated flavone, β -cryptoxanthin (152) and archidonate cyclooxy-

Table 1. Flavonoids presents in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
3,5,6,7,8,3',4'-Heptamethoxyflavone	1	<i>C. clementina</i> ²⁵ , <i>C. depressa</i> ²⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁷ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ¹¹
3,5,6,7,3',4'-Hexamethoxyflavone	2	<i>C. reticulata</i> ^{28,29} , <i>C. clementina</i> ²⁵
3,5,7,8,3',4'-Hexamethoxyflavone	3	<i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁹
5,6,7,8,3',4'-Hexamethoxyflavone	4	<i>C. unshiu</i> ³⁰
5,7,8,4'-Tetramethoxyflavone	5	<i>C. unshiu</i> ³¹
5,7,4'-Trimethoxyflavone	6	<i>C. reticulata</i> ³²
3'-Hydroxy-5,6,7,8,4'-pentamethoxyflavone	7	<i>C. reticulata</i> ³³
5-Hydroxy-3,7,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone	8	<i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁹
5-Hydroxy-6,7,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone	9	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{27,30}
5-Hydroxy-7,8,4'-trimethoxyflavone	10	<i>C. nobilis</i> ³⁴
7-Hydroxy-5,6,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone	11	<i>C. reticulata</i> ³⁵
7,4'-Dihydroxy-5,6,8,3'-tetramethoxyflavone	12	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ³⁶
4'-Hydroxy-5,6,7,8-tetramethoxyflavone	13	<i>C. nobilis</i> ³⁴
4'-Dihydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone	14	<i>C. reticulata</i> ³⁷
5,7,8,3',4'-Pentamethoxyflavone	15	<i>C. unshiu</i> ³⁰
3-Hydroxy-5,6,7,8,3',4'-hexamethoxyflavone-3-O-β-D-glucoside	16	<i>C. unshiu</i> ³⁸
3,7,4'-Trihydroxy-5,6,8,3'-tetramethoxyflavone-3-O-β-D-glucoside	17	<i>C. unshiu</i> ³⁸
6,8-Di-C-β-D-glucopyranosylapigenin (vicenin-2)	18	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{38,39}
Acerosin	19	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴⁰
Citflavanone	20	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴¹
Citromitin	21	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴²
Citrunobin	22	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴¹
Citrusinol	23	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴³
6-Demethoxynobiletin	24	<i>C. depressa</i> ^{26,44}
6-Demethoxytangertin	25	<i>C. depressa</i> ^{26,44}
5-O-Desmethylcitromitin	26	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴²
5-O-Demethylnobiletin	27	<i>C. depressa</i> ^{26,44} , <i>C. reticulata</i> ³¹ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁵ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ³⁶
Diosmin	28	<i>C. erythroa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. depressa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reshni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. sunki</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tumida</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tachibana</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁶
Eriocitrin	29	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. erythroa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. keraji</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. kinokuni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. leiocarpa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. oto</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reshni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. succosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. suhuiensis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. sunki</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tachibana</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tardiva</i> ⁴⁶
Hesperdin	30	<i>C. reticulata</i> ^{42,47} , <i>C. unshiu</i> ³⁸
Hesperetin 7-neohesperidoside	31	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁸
Hesperetin 7-rutinoside	32	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁸
Isohoifolin	33	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. kinokuni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reshni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁶
Isosinensetin	34	<i>C. reshni</i> ⁴⁵
Kaemferol	35	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁴⁵
Limocitrin 3-β-D-glucoside	36	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{38,49}
Limocitrin 3-α-L-rhamnoside	37	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁹
Luteolin	38	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. erythroa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴⁶
Luteolin 7-rutinoside	39	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{38,50}

Naringenin	40	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁶
Naringin	41	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴⁷
Narirutin	42	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴⁷ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{38,49}
Natsudaidain	43	<i>C. depressa</i> ²⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ¹¹
Neodiosmin	44	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶
Neoneriocitrin	45	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. erythroa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. keraji</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. kinokuni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. leiocarpa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. oto</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reshni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{46,47} , <i>C. succosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. suhuiensis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. sunki</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tachibana</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tardiva</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. yatsusiro</i> ⁴⁶
Neohesperidin	46	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴²
Neoponcirin	47	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. depressa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. erythroa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. keraji</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. kinokuni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. leiocarpa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. oto</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reshni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. succosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. suhuiensis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. sunki</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tachibana</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tardiva</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. yatsusiro</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tumida</i>
Nobiletin	48	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ³⁶ , <i>C. depressa</i> ^{26,44} , <i>C. clementina</i> ²⁵ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ¹¹ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{28,27}
Poncirin	49	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tachibana</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tumida</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁶
Ponkanetin	50	<i>C. reticulata</i> ³¹
Quercetin	51	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. depressa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. kinokuni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. oto</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. succosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. suhuiensis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. sunki</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. yatsusiro</i>
Rhoifolin	52	<i>C. kinokuni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. succosa</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i>
Rutin	53	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{38,50}
Sinensetin	54	<i>C. clementina</i> ²⁵ , <i>C. depressa</i> ^{26,44} , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{27,28}
Takakin	55	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁵¹
Tangeretin	56	<i>C. clementina</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ³⁶ , <i>C. depressa</i> ^{26,44} , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁴² , <i>C. nobilis</i> ¹² , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{27,28}
Taxifolin	57	<i>C. kinokuni</i> ⁴⁶ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴⁶
Tetra- <i>O</i> -methylscutellarein	58	<i>C. clementina</i> ²⁵ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁵

genase (COX) and lipoxygenase (LOX) inhibitors. Flavonoids are known to act as antioxidants and show anti-cancer activity¹⁴ to protect against lipid peroxidation^{15,16} to possess anti-inflammatory properties^{17,18} and to produce anticarcinogenic effect^{19,20}.

Attaway²¹ revealed that α -thujene (97) and sabinene (93) found in *C. tangerina* peel oils. Terpenoids (Table 2) such as limonene (82) and geraniol (79) have been reported to be effective in the inhibition of pancreatic or mammary cancer growth²². It was also reported that the administration of terpene hydrocarbons such as limonene (82) and carvone (65) to mice reduced the occurrence of cancer because of increased activity of glutathione S-transferase^{23,24}.

Table 2. Terpenoids presents in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
α -Amyrin	59	<i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁹
β -Bisabolene	60	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵²
γ -Cadinene	61	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³
δ -Cadinene	62	<i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Camphene	63	<i>C. clementina</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Carveol	64	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵³
Carvone	65	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Caryophyllene	66	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
β -Caryophyllene	67	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵²
δ -3-Carene	68	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸

		Table-2 (contd.)
α -Copaene	69	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Citronellal	70	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
α -Cubebene	71	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁵⁶
β -Cubebene	72	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
<i>p</i> -Cymene	73	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁵⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁵⁷ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
α -Elemene	74	<i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ²⁸
δ -Elemene	75	<i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{28,54}
α -Farnesene	76	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
β -Farnesene	77	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵
Friedelin	78	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁰
Geraniol	79	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Germacene-D	80	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{28,58}
Humulene	81	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Limonene	82	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁶¹ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{28,56} , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁶² , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{28,56-58}
Linalool	83	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Myrcene	84	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁶¹ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{28,56} , <i>C. tangerina</i> ^{57,62} , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Neral	85	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Nootkatone	86	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
α -Phellandrene	87	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵²
β -Phellandrene	88	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³
α -Pinene	89	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{28,56} , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁵⁹ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{28,54,58}
β -Pinene	90	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{28,56} , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁵⁹ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{28,54,58}
Piperitone	91	<i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Perialdehyde	92	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Sabinene	93	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{56,62} , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁵⁷ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
β -Selinene	94	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
α -Sinensal	95	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
β -Sinensal	96	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
α -Thujene	97	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸

		Table-2 (contd.)
α -Terpinene	98	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁵⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁵⁷ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
γ -Terpinene	99	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁵⁶ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁵⁷ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
α -Terpineol	100	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵⁵ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
Terpinolene	101	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁵⁶ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ^{28,54}
Terpine-4-ol	102	<i>C. clementina</i> ⁵³ , <i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁵² , <i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁸ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ²⁸
<i>trans-trans</i> - α -farnesene	103	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}

Table 3. Alkaloids in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
Citraacidone-I	104	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁴³ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ⁶³
Citraacidone-II	105	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³
Citropone A	106	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁴³
Citpressine-I	107	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³
Citpressine-II	108	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³
Citrusinine-I	109	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁴³
5-Hydroxynoracronycine	110	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁶³ , <i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³
<i>N</i> , α' , <i>N'</i> , α -Cyclodi-(4-methylamino-benzene)ethanol	111	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁴
12-Methylataphyllidine	112	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶⁵
Prenylcitpressine	113	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³

Table 4. Coumarins in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
Casegravol isovalerate	114	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁶
Citropten	115	<i>Mandarin species</i> ⁶⁷
Clausarin	116	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³
6,7-Dimethoxycoumarin	117	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁶⁸
(<i>E</i>)-Suberenol	118	<i>C. nobilis</i> ⁶⁹
Suberosin	119	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ^{34,43}
<i>trans</i> -grandmarin	120	<i>C. unshiu</i> x <i>C. sinensis</i> ⁷⁰
Nordentatin	121	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³
Xanthyletin	122	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³ , <i>C. nobilis</i> ³⁴ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷¹
Xanthoxyletin	123	<i>C. depressa</i> ⁶³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷¹

Others major chemical constituents include alkaloids (Table 3); limonoids (Table 4); coumarins (Table 5); steroids (Table 6); carotenoids (Table 7); gibberellins

(Table 8); esters (Table 9); acids (Table 10); alcohols and aldehydes (Table 11). Sugars, amino acids, alkyl glycosides and ketones are tabulated in Table 12 under the heading miscellaneous constituents.

Table 5. Limonoids in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
Deacteylnomilin	124	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷² , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷³
Deacteylnomilinic acid	125	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷²
Ichangin	126	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷²
Isolimononic acid	127	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷³
Isolimonexic acid methyl ether	128	<i>C. reticulata</i>
Limonin	129	<i>C. tangerina</i> ^{73,74}
Nomilin	130	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁴ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷³
Nomilinic acid	131	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷³
Obacunone	132	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁴ , <i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷³
Deacteylnomilinic acid-17-β-D-glucopyranoside	133	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁵
Deacteylnomilin-17-β-D-glucopyranoside	134	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁵
Ichangin-17-β-D-glucopyranoside	135	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁵
Limonin-17-β-D-glucopyranoside	136	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁵
Nomilin-17-β-D-glucopyranoside	137	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁵
Nomilinic acid-17-β-D-glucopyranoside	138	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁵
Obacunone-17-β-D-glucopyranoside	139	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁵

Table 6. Steroids in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
Brassicasterol	140	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁷⁶
Campesterol	141	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{76,77} , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{31,78}
Cholesterol	142	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{76,77} , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{31,78}
23-Dehydrocholesterol	143	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁷⁶
24-Methylcholesterol	144	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁷⁶
Sitosterol	145	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁷⁶ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁷⁸
β-Sitosterol	146	<i>C. reticulata</i> ³¹
Stigmasterol	147	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁷⁷ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ³¹

Table 7. Carotenoids in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
α-Carotene	148	<i>C. tangerina</i> ^{79,80}
β-Carotene	149	<i>C. tangerina</i> ^{79,80}
γ-Carotene	150	<i>C. tangerina</i> ^{79,80}

α-Cryptoxanthin	151	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁸⁰
β-Cryptoxanthin	152	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷⁹
Lutein	153	<i>C. tangerina</i> ^{79,80}
Lycopene	154	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷⁹
Phytoene	155	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷⁹
Phytofluene	156	<i>C. tangerina</i> ^{79,80}
Provitamin-A	157	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁸⁰
Reticulataxanthin	158	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁸⁰
Violaxanthin	159	<i>C. tangerina</i> ^{79,80}
Zeaxanthin	160	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁷⁹

Table-7 (contd.)

Table 8. Gibberellins in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
Gibberellin A ₁	161	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹
Gibberellin A ₄	162	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹
Gibberellin A ₉	163	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹
Gibberellin A ₁₉	164	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹
Gibberellin A ₂₀	165	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹
Gibberellin A ₂₄	166	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹
Gibberellin A ₄₄	167	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹
Gibberellin A ₅₃	168	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸¹

Table 9. Esters in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
Decyl acetate	169	<i>C. clementina</i>
Dodecyl acetate	170	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Ethyl benzoate	171	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Ethyl palmitate	172	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Ethyl stearate	173	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Ethyl propionate	174	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
Heptyl acetate	175	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Methyl benzoate	176	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Methyl palmitate	177	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Methyl oleate	178	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Methyl pentadecanoate	179	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Methyl stearate	180	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Nonyl acetate	181	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Octyl acetate	182	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
β-Phenethyl acetate	183	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸

Table 10. Acids in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
2-Hexenoic acid	184	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
2-Nonenoic acid	185	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
3-Phenyl propionic acid	186	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Benzoic acid	187	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Capric acid	188	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸

Table-10 (contd.)

Caproic acid	189	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Caprylic acid	190	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Ferulic acid	191	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁵
Lauric acid	192	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Linoleic acid	193	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{29,82}
Linolenic acid	194	<i>C. reticulata</i> ²⁹
Myristic acid	195	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Oleic acid	196	<i>C. reticulata</i> ^{29,82}
Palmitic acid	197	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{29,82}
<i>p</i> -Coumaric acid	198	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁵
Pentadecanoic acid	199	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Phenylacetic acid	200	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
<i>p</i> -Toulic acid	201	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Sinapic acid	202	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁴⁵
Stearic acid	203	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸³ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ^{29,82}
Undecanoic acid	204	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸

Table 11. Alcohols and aldehydes in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
β-Phenethylalcohol	205	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
2-(4-Methylphenyl)-2-propanol	206	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁸⁵
Benzaldehyde	207	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Benzyl alcohol	208	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Decanal	209	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Dodecanal	210	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Heptanal	211	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Hexanal	212	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Hexanol	213	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Menthol	214	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Nerol	215	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Nonanal	216	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
Octanal	217	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Piperitol	218	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
<i>trans</i> -2-hexenol	219	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
<i>trans</i> -2-pentenol	220	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Undecanal	221	<i>C. unshiu</i> ^{54,58}
Vanillin	222	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
α-(Methylamino)methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl methanol	223	<i>C. reticulata</i> ⁸⁵

Table 12. Miscellaneous compounds in mandarin species

Compound	Structure	Plants
Acetaphenone	224	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
Adenosine	225	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁴

Table-12 (contd.)

Benzyl cyanide	226	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Bufotenine	227	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁶
Bufotenine-5- <i>O</i> -β-D-glucopyranoside	228	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁶
Coniferin	229	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁷
Citrusin A	230	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁷
Citrusin B	231	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁷
Citrusin C	232	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁷
Citrusin D	233	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁷
Citroside A	234	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁰
Citroside B	235	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁰
Dehydrodiconiferyl alcohol-4-β-glucoside	236	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁷
Diacetonamine	237	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁸⁸
Ethyl-1-β-glucopyranoside	238	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁴
3-Ethyl-4-methylpyridine	239	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Glucopyranose	240	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸³
Glucose	241	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴³
Hexyl-β-glucosyl-(1→6)-β-apiose	242	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁴
Hexyl-1-β-glucopyranoside	243	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁴
5-Hydroxy- <i>N</i> _w -methyl tryptamine	244	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁶
Indole acetic acid	245	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁹
Indole acetamide	246	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁹
Indole	247	<i>C. deliciosa</i> ⁹⁰ , <i>C. reticulata</i> ⁹⁰ , <i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Methyl heptenone	248	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁴
6-Methyl-5-hepten-2-one	249	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
β-Phenylnitroethane	250	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Phenyl acetaldoxime	251	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁵⁸
Propyl-1-β-glucopyranoside	252	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁶⁴
L-Rhamnose	253	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁴⁸
Syringin	254	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁸⁷
Synephrine	255	<i>C. unshiu</i> ⁹¹
Triacetanamine	256	<i>C. tangerina</i> ⁸⁸

- 1 $R_3 = R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = \text{OMe}$
- 2 $R_3 = R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = \text{OMe}; R_8 = \text{H}$
- 3 $R_3 = R_5 = R_8 = R_7 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = \text{OMe}; R_6 = \text{H}$
- 4 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = \text{OMe}; R_3 = \text{H}$
- 5 $R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{4'} = \text{OMe}; R_3 = R_6 = R_{3'} = \text{H}$
- 6 $R_{4'} = R_5 = R_7 = \text{OMe}; R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = \text{H}$

- 7 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_{3'} = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 8 $R_3 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = OH$; $R_6 = H$
 9 $R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 10 $R_7 = R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = OH$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_{3'} = H$
 11 $R_5 = R_6 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_7 = OH$; $R_3 = R_8 = H$
 12 $R_5 = R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = OMe$; $R_7 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 13 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = OMe$; $R_{4'} = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 14 $R_7 = R_8 = OMe$; $R_5 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_{3'} = H$
 15 $R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = R_6 = H$
 16 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = O\text{-glu}$
 17 $R_5 = R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = OMe$; $R_7 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_3 = O\text{-glu}$
 18 $R_5 = R_7 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_6 = R_8 = O\text{-glu}$; $R_3 = R_{3'} = H$
 19 $R_6 = R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_7 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 24 $R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_6 = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 25 $R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_6 = OH$; $R_3 = R_{3'} = H$
 27 $R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 28 $R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-rutinose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = H$
 33 $R_5 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-rutinose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = H$
 34 $R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_6 = R_3 = H$
 35 $R_3 = R_5 = R_7 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = H$
 36 $R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_7 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_3 = O\text{-glu}$; $R_6 = H$
 37 $R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_7 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_3 = O\text{-rham}$; $R_6 = H$
 38 $R_5 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = H$
 39 $R_5 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-rutinose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = H$
 43 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = OH$
 44 $R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_7 = \text{neohesperidose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = H$
 48 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = H$
 50 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = R_{3'} = H$
 51 $R_3 = R_5 = R_7 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_6 = R_8 = H$
 52 $R_5 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-neohesperidose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = H$
 53 $R_5 = R_7 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_3 = O\text{-rutinose}$; $R_6 = R_8 = H$
 54 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = R_8 = H$
 55 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = OH$; $R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = R_{3'} = H$
 56 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = R_{3'} = H$
 58 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = R_8 = R_{3'} = H$

- 21 $R_5 = R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_3 = H$
 26 $R_6 = R_7 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = OH$
 29 $R_3 = R_5 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-rutinose}$; $R_6 = R_8 = H$

- 30 $R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-rutinose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = H$
 31 $R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-neohesperidose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = H$
 32 $R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-rutinose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = H$
 40 $R_3 = R_5 = R_7 = OH$; $R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = H$
 42 $R_5 = R_{4'} = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-neohesperidose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = H$
 47 $R_{4'} = OMe$; $R_5 = OH$; $R_7 = O\text{-neohesperidose}$; $R_3 = R_6 = R_8 = R_{3'} = H$
 57 $R_3 = R_5 = R_7 = R_{3'} = OH$; $R_6 = R_8 = R_{4'} = H$

- 41 $R_3 = R_{3'} = R_{4'} = H$
 45 $R_{4'} = R_3 = H$; $R_{3'} = OH$
 46 $R_3 = H$; $R_{3'} = OH$; $R_{4'} = OMe$
 49 $R_3 = R_{3'} = H$; $R_{4'} = Me$

- 20 $R = H$
 23 $R = OH$

22

- 104 $R_1 = OMe$; $R_2 = R_4 = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 105 $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$; $R_4 = OH$; $R_3 = H$
 106 $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = COMe$; $R_3 = R_4 = OH$
 110 $R_1 = R_4 = OH$; $R_2 = R_3 = H$
 112 $R_1 = OH$; $R_2 = Me$; $R_3 = R_4 = H$

113

- 107 $R_1 = R_6 = OH; R_3 = R_5 = OMe; R_2 = R_4 = H$
 108 $R_1 = OH; R_3 = R_5 = R_6 = OMe; R_2 = R_4 = H$
 109 $R_1 = R_5 = OH; R_3 = R_4 = OMe; R_2 = R_6 = H$

111

114

- 115 $R_5 = R_7 = OMe; R_6 = R_8 = H$
 117 $R_6 = R_7 = OMe; R_5 = R_8 = H$
 118 $R_7 = OMe; R_6 = CH:CH.C(Me)_2OH; R_5 = R_8 = H$

116

- 122 $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 123 $R_1 = R_3 = H; R_2 = OMe$

119

120

121

- 124 $R = H$
 130 $R = Ac$

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125 R₁ = OH; R₂ = H
 131 R₁ = OAc; R₂ = H

132

126

133 R = H
 138 R = Ac

127

134

128

135

129

137

139

150

141 $R_1 = \alpha\text{-Me}; R_2 = \text{OH}$

142 $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OH}$

143 $R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = \text{OH}$

147 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3; R_2 = \text{OH}$

154

155

156

144

157

145 $R = \text{CH}_3$

146 $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$

162

163

140

167

- 164 $R_1 = \text{OH}, R_2 = \text{CHO}, R_3 = \text{Me}$
 166 $R_2 = \text{CHO}, R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 168 $R_2 = R_3 = \text{Me}, R_1 = \text{OH}$

- 171 $R_1 = \text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3; R_2 = \text{H}$
 176 $R_1 = \text{COOCH}_3; R_2 = \text{H}$
 183 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_3; R_2 = \text{H}$
 186 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}, R_2 = \text{H}$
 187 $R_1 = \text{COOH}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 200 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{COOH}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 201 $R_1 = \text{COOH}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 205 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 207 $R_1 = \text{CHO}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 208 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{OH}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 224 $R_1 = \text{COMe}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 226 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CN}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 250 $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2; R_1 = \text{H}$
 251 $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH:NOH}; R_1 = \text{H}$

- 191 $R_1 = \text{OH}; R_4 = \text{CH:CH.COOH}; R_6 = \text{OMe}; R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = \text{H}$
 198 $R_1 = \text{OH}; R_4 = \text{CH:CH.COOH}; R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$
 202 $R_2 = \text{CH:CH.COOH}; R_4 = R_6 = \text{OMe}; R_5 = \text{OH}; R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 222 $R_1 = \text{CHO}; R_3 = \text{OMe}; R_4 = \text{OH}; R_2 = R_5 = R_6 = \text{H}$

- 175 $n = 6$
 182 $n = 7$
 181 $n = 8$
 169 $n = 9$
 170 $n = 11$

- 184 $n = 4$
 185 $n = 5$

- 161 $R = \text{OH}$
 165 $R = \text{H}$

193

194

- 172 $n = 14; R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$
 173 $n = 16; R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$
 174 $n = 0; R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$
 177 $n = 14; R = \text{CH}_3$
 179 $n = 13; R = \text{CH}_3$
 180 $n = 16; R = \text{CH}_3$
 188 $n = 8; R = \text{H}$
 189 $n = 4; R = \text{H}$
 190 $n = 6; R = \text{H}$
 192 $n = 10; R = \text{H}$
 195 $n = 12; R = \text{H}$
 197 $n = 14; R = \text{H}$
 199 $n = 13; R = \text{H}$
 203 $n = 16; R = \text{H}$
 204 $n = 9; R = \text{H}$

- 196 $R = \text{H}$
 178 $R = \text{CH}_3$

242

237

236

- 227 $R_2 = \text{OH}; R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{OCH}_3)_2$
 228 $R_2 = \text{O-glu}; R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{OCH}_3)_2$
 244 $R_2 = \text{OH}; R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$
 245 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{COOH}; R_2 = \text{H}$
 246 $R_1 = \text{CH}_2\text{CONH}_2; R_2 = \text{H}$
 247 $R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = \text{H}$

- 230 $R = \text{H}$
 231 $R = \text{OMe}$

225

256

- 234 $R = \text{H}; R_1 = \text{Ac}$
 235 $R = \text{Ac}; R_1 = \text{H}$

- 238 $R_1 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5; R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$
 243 $R_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}; R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$
 252 $R_1 = \text{C}_3\text{H}_5; R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$
 241 $R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$
 253 $R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = \text{CH}_3$

239

248

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255

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223

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237

242

219 R = CH₂ CH₂ CH₃

220 R = CH₂ CH₂ CH₃

244

232

229 R₁ = OMe, R₂ = OH, R₃ = H

233 R₁ = OH, R₂ = OMe; R₃ = H

254 R₁ = R₃ = OMe, R₂ = OH

240

214

218

206

	X	Y
148	d	b
149	d	d
151	e	b
152	e	d
153	e	c
158	e	CH:CHAc
159	f	f
160	e	e

(b) R = H
(c) R = OH

(d) R = H
(e) R = OH

(f)

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